

Vision Transformer for Classification of Breast Cancer Ultrasound Images

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ABSTRACT

The proposed paper aims to use the computer-aided CAD system for the early detection of a breast cancer and classification tumor type. The main idea of the proposed paper is ultrasound image classification by using Vision Transformer (ViT). ViT can be trained to classify breast cancer by ultrasound images. ViT may aid diagnosing breast cancer on different images with an accuracy comparable to radiologists. Vision Transformer (ViT) designs, based on self-attention between image patches, have shown great potential to be an alternative to CNNs.

Keywords— Vision Transformer; Breast Cancer; Classification; Diagnostic Image.

1. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer disease was discovered since more than 3500 years ago by the Ancient Egyptians [1]. Recently, Breast cancer death rate have been decreasing since 1989, Also, Over the last three decades, there has been a substantial decline in breast cancer mortality [2]. The 2020 report of World Cancer Research fund shows that there were more than 2 million newly diagnosed breast cancer cases in 2018 [3].

The proposed paper domain is ultrasound image classification by using Vision Transformer (ViT). The Vision Transformer (ViT) appeared as another alternative to convolutional neural networks (CNNs) that are certainly state-of-the-art in computer vision and hence broadly in different image recognition tasks. ViT models exceed the standard state-of-the-art (CNN) by about x4 in terms of computational efficiency and accuracy.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1. Review of Related Work

Behnaz Gheflati et al. In [4]. Proposed the implementation of ViT to classify breast US images using different augmentation strategies. The authors used pre-

trained models such as R+Ti/16, S/32, B/32, Ti/16 and R26+s/16. Where B/32 was achieving the best-trained model. The system performs with an 86% Acc and 0.95 AUC.

Jari Lindroos. In [5]. Proposed to evaluate the performance of vision transducer models by comparing them to CNNs. The author used both the conventional transfer learning-based approach and a pre-training approach based on domain adaptation such as ResNet-50, Ti/16, S/32, S/16, B/16, R+Ti/16, R26+S/32. Where the best AUC score is 0.97315 for the ViT B/16 model.

Gelan Ayana et al. in [6]. Proposed the present BUViTNet breast ultrasound detection. Where ViT-based multistage transfer learning is performed using ImageNet and cancer cell image datasets prior to transfer learning for classifying breast ultrasound images. The authors used pre-trained models such as ViTb_16, ViTb_32 and ViTI_32. The vitb_16 model achieved the highest AUC of 0.937.

3. Vision Transformer (ViT)

The Vision Transformer (ViT) appeared as another alternative to convolutional neural networks (CNNs) that are certainly state-of-the-art in computer vision and hence broadly in different image recognition tasks. ViT models exceed the standard state-of-the-art (CNN) by about x4 in terms of computational efficiency and accuracy.

Vision Transformers (ViT) have accomplished much competitive performance in standards for multiple computer vision applications, such as image classification, object detection, and semantic image segmentation.

Vision transformers have many applications in a variety of image recognition tasks. In addition, vision transformers are used for Generative Modelling and Multi-Model Tasks with Visual Grounding, Visual Question Respondent and Visual Reasoning. Image Foretelling and Activity Recognition are all components of image processing

that need vision transformers [7].

Fig. 1. Architecture of Vision Transformer.

4. Convolutional neural networks

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are important network types in the field of deep learning, and CNN has received a lot of attention from industry and academia over the past years due to its outstanding achievements in many areas, not just in the field of computer monitoring and natural language processing.

One of the most attractive qualities of CNN is its ability to exploit spatial or temporal correlation in data. A set of convolutional layers, nonlinear processing units, and sub-viewing layers make up each of the many learning steps that make up a CNN. CNN is a hierarchical multi-layer front-end network in which each layer uses a bank of convolutional kernels to implement a few changes.

Fig. 2. CNN Architecture.

5. METHODS

5.1. Agile Development

The project implements system functionality using agile software development methodologies. The Agile methodology breaks the system up into several phases. In the agile methodology, the software development is made up of iterations. In each iteration, part of the software product is developed. Each iteration consists of six steps which are requirements, design, development, testing, deployment, and review.

5.2. Dataset

The dataset used in this study includes two different datasets. The first dataset collected includes breast ultrasound images among women between the ages of 25 and 75. In 2018, this data was collected. Where the number of patients reached 600 patients. The dataset consists of 780 images with an average size of 500x500 pixels. The images are in PNG format. The images are divided into three categories: normal, benign, and malignant. The source of dataset is Baheya Hospital for Early Detection & Treatment of Women’s Cancer, Cairo, Egypt. By Professor Ali Fahmy [8]. The second dataset contains X-Ray images of patients suffering from Pneumonia in comparison with X-Ray images referring to normal condition. The dataset consists of 5863 images and two classes (Normal, Pneumonia).[9] The source of dataset: <https://www.kaggle.com/paultimothymooney/chest-xray-pneumonia/home>.

6. RESULTS

We tested the ViT and CNN models to classify breast ultrasound image into three categories: benign, malignant, and normal. And chest X-ray images into two categories: normal and pneumonia. Table 1 shows the classification result for ViT model in different batches. The classification accuracy result for CNN model is reported in Table 2.

Table 1. The performance of the ViT model

Dataset	14x14	16x16	32x32
BUSI	38%	84%	81%
Chest x-ray	-	89%	-

Table 2. The performance of the CNN model

Dataset	Acc
BUSI	70%
Chest x-ray	89%

7. CONCLUSION

The proposed paper reviewed and compared many vision transformer techniques currently available in the market for the early detection of breast cancer. This project proposes a computer-aided (CAD) system for the detection of early breast cancer from ultrasound images using the Vision Transformer. This system helps to avoid a lot of time and effort required for medical diagnosis. The main idea of the proposed system is image classifications of the tumor types and divide them into three cases which are Normal, Benign, and Malignant.

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